

The Future of Learning: Integrating Robotic Efficiency for Enhanced Educational Efficacy

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Abstract:

The Covid-19 pandemic has posed learning barriers for communities in Indonesia and around the world. It has disrupted normal teaching and learning activities, necessitating the adoption of distance learning. Students face challenges during distance learning, including low motivation to succeed and complete online classes, as well as difficulty in handling encountered problems or difficulties. Robotics was chosen as a learning medium because it has been proven to stimulate self-efficacy. The development of self-efficacy among students is crucial in distance learning implementation as it can help overcome barriers that arise during the learning process. This research aims to implement robotics media in distance learning while considering media accessibility and self-efficacy. The research methodology employed is a field case study with qualitative descriptive data analysis techniques. The results of the study indicate that with the use of robotics media, student enthusiasm level reached 92%, and 92% of students fully comprehended the presented learning materials. The implementation of distance learning using robotics media was highly successful, with 92% of students expressing increased diligence in their studies, and 96% of students striving to improve their grades. Student self-efficacy was also relatively high, with 88% of students showing confidence in their ability to engage in learning. The use of robotics media aided students in distance learning, with a 100% completion rate and satisfactory achievement results. Additionally, it was found that the inclusion of illustrations had an impact on students' confidence in completing tasks correctly and accurately. more tangible and accessible.

Keywords: *Distance Learning, Educational Robotic, Self-efficacy.*

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Introduction

Learning is a process of interaction between students, educators, and learning resources within a learning environment, encompassing the exchange of information between teachers and students. Learning involves acquiring new behaviors or strengthening/weakening existing behaviors as a result of experience. David (1996: 86) states that learning is a process in which organisms change their behavior as a result of experience. Experience can be gained through learning because students can acquire knowledge and skills essential for their lives. In other words, learning is a process for teachers to impart skills and knowledge to provide experiences to students so they can change their behavior. In delivering these skills and knowledge, there are many methods that teachers can choose based on students' criteria, learning objectives, and the current situation faced by both teachers and students.

Distance learning, also known as remote learning, is implemented when students and teachers cannot meet face-to-face in the classroom due to certain barriers. Like the learning barriers experienced by Indonesian and global communities due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which has prevented teachers and students from meeting in person to prevent the spread of the virus. In response to these barriers, on March 24, 2020, the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia issued Circular Letter Number 4 of 2020 Regarding the Implementation of Education Policies During the Emergency Period of the Spread of the Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19). Following this Circular Letter, teachers and students were required to implement distance learning to curb the spread of the Covid-19 virus.

One challenge in distance learning is that many students may struggle to handle difficulties encountered during the learning process (Croft, Dalton, & Grant, 2010; Gnawali, Upadhayaya, Sharma, & Belbase, 2022). Additionally, motivation to succeed and complete online classes may be lacking among students (Bolliger & Martin, 2021; Murphy & Rodriguez Manzanares, 2012). Self-efficacy becomes crucial in distance learning as it can address these challenges. Self-efficacy guides students' feelings, thoughts, motivation, and behavior, and is a significant factor contributing to student persistence (Litton, Goodridge, Call, & Lopez, 2018). Low self-efficacy can hinder individuals from initiating new tasks.

From the above exposition, it is concluded that self-efficacy are essential competencies for students to support the implementation of distance learning. Robotics media can be used to provide stimulus to students to cultivate both of these skills. In the study by Master et al. (Master, Cheryan, Moscatelli, & Meltzoff, 2017) involving elementary school students, the use of robotics had a positive impact on self-efficacy. Similarly, in the study by Kaloti-Hallak et al. (Kaloti-Hallak, Armoni, & Ben-Ari, 2015) involving junior high school students, it was found that the use of robotics had a positive impact on self-efficacy. White (Vemitra, Jamel Hill, & Debra, 2017) conducted research with junior high school and high school students, and the results showed that students could improve their self-efficacy through robotics. Furthermore, the study by Leonard et al. (Leonard et al., 2017) involving high school teachers demonstrated that the self-efficacy of teachers increased after using robotics. Overall, the use of robotics has a positive effect on self-efficacy.

Then there are several types of robotics media that can be used to support the learning process and provide stimulus to self-efficacy. Among several types of robotics, Arduino is chosen as the robotics media for this research with several considerations: (1) Arduino IDE is freely available (Open Source) for Windows, Linux, and Mac; (2) It is very easy to modify and update programs as it is connected to the PC via USB; (3) Arduino is part of a large online community with many references and example scripts; (4) Arduino is highly flexible and offers various digital input/output and analog serial interface; (5) Arduino offers affordable prices, making it a low-cost robotic (Hertzog & Swart, 2016) With the considerations above, Arduino is chosen as the media to be used.

This research aims to further analyze the implementation of distance learning, the utilization of robotics, as well as self-efficacy. Therefore, the researcher endeavors to implement distance learning using robotics media in the Contemporary Information Technology subject. Contemporary Information Technology is one of the subjects in the Software Engineering specialization of the Computer Engineering Education program at Sebelas Maret University. Distance learning is implemented using the LMS Schoology as the instructional platform. The research is conducted by designing and developing jobsheets while considering the suitability of the selected robotics devices. It is hoped that the use of new devices and methods can make the learning process more effective. This research is expected to serve as a reference for improving the quality of learning and education in Indonesia, especially in relation to distance learning.

Research Method

This research was conducted at the Informatics and Computer Engineering Education Study Program (PTIK) Sebelas Maret University, Surakarta. This research involved 24 students taking Contemporary Information Engineering courses. These 24 students were then grouped into two categories. The first category uses modules equipped with

illustration images, while the second category uses modules without illustration images. The division into this category is based on their Student Identification Number (NIM). Students with odd NIMs use modules that have illustrative images, while students with even NIMs use modules without illustrative images. Table 1 shows the student group categories:

Table 1. Student Group Categories

Category	Number of Students	Module	Group
Odd	12	Modules with Illustrative Images	Group A
Even	12	Modules without Illustrative Images	Group B

Student self-efficacy research data in the form of qualitative data was analyzed using qualitative descriptive analysis developed by Miles and Huberman. The steps used are to create simple coding. Codes are tags or labels to assign meaning to descriptive information compiled during a study. Codes are usually chunks of words, phrases, sentences, or entire paragraphs of various sizes, connected or unconnected to specific settings. The results of this process are expected to be able to look for contrasts and classify students into certain criteria groups. In the process of drawing conclusions, the level of student self-efficacy in each self-efficacy category can be shown.

Table 2. Self Efficacy Interview Grid

Aspect	Indicators	Question Items
Level	Maintain a positive attitude toward the things you are completing.	2
	Ability to take suitable measures.	3
Strength	Confident in one's ability to overcome challenges within the task's difficulty level.	2
	Using life experience as a step towards success.	1
	Capable of maintaining a pleasant mood in a variety of settings.	2
Generality	Display a confident attitude throughout the learning process.	2
	Have strong self-confidence in the capacity to complete assignments.	3
	Have a fighting spirit and do not give up easily when faced with challenges in completing a task.	1
	Make a commitment to completing academic assignments successfully.	2

Result and Analysis

The development of Robotics Media in this research is focused on learning through distance learning. There are several learning models that can be applied in the context of distance learning, and in this research, researchers used the PjBL (Project-based Learning) model. The robotics media that will be developed is based on the chosen learning model, namely the PjBL model. Therefore, researchers developed media in the form of robots along with modules containing projects that students could learn in stages.

The robotics media developed is the Arduino UNO R3 robot. Arduino UNO R3 was chosen because this type of microprocessor is easy to use and has an affordable price. This media was developed together with a usage module to help students participate in learning. This module is made in two types, where the difference lies in the presence of images of tools and materials. The first module is equipped with pictures of tools and materials, while the second module is not. This difference can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Arduino Module

The purpose of having two types of modules is to observe whether images and illustrations have an impact on students' self-efficacy and computational thinking. In the implementation process, Scratch is used as the programming tool for students to create a project sequence. The development of robotics media and modules follows the ADDIE approach.

As previously elaborated, self-efficacy criteria are divided into three categories, each with its own set of indicators. Detailed information on each criterion and its indicators can be found in Table 2. Subsequently, an analysis is conducted based on these criteria and indicators.

Level

For the level aspect, there are 3 indicators. Based on these indicators, several questions were developed. The results of the interview analysis for each indicator are as follows:

Positive Attitude Towards the Task at Hand

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 2 interview questions, namely about students' enthusiasm for attending classes and their confidence in analyzing projects. In the interview results for question 1 in Group A, the number of students who were very enthusiastic about attending classes was 1, while 9 students expressed enthusiasm and 2 others stated they were less enthusiastic. The enthusiastic students cited their ability to learn new things. Most of the 9 enthusiastic students mentioned that with the presence of tangible practical tools, they could easily follow the lessons. The 2 students who expressed less enthusiasm did so because of the excessive amount of assignments given. In Group B, all 12 students or the entire group expressed enthusiasm for the IoT (Internet of Things) class. Reasons cited included the availability of practical tools that could be used directly, the presence of easily understandable modules and practical tools, and students' interest in applying IoT to daily life. The interview results showed that using different types of modules led to varying levels of enthusiasm among students. Comparing Group A, which used illustrated modules, with Group B, which used modules without illustrations, students in Group B were actually more enthusiastic about learning the subject being taught.

In the interview results for question 2 regarding students' confidence in analyzing projects, in Group A, 9 students expressed confidence in analyzing projects, while 3 others expressed less confidence. One student who expressed confidence mentioned that there are many learning resources available to help with project analysis. In Group B, 11 students expressed confidence in analyzing projects, while 1 expressed less confidence. The student who expressed less confidence mentioned that repeated practice is needed to understand projects thoroughly so that they can confidently analyze or dissect them. From the interview results of these two groups, students in Group B were more dominant in having confidence in analyzing projects compared to Group A.

Confidence in Taking Necessary Actions

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 3 interview questions assessing students' confidence in evaluating work, confidence in creating a project, and confidence in completing difficult tasks.

In Group A, 8 out of 12 students expressed confidence in evaluating work, with one student stating that they could evaluate their classmates' work and even predict potential errors in their projects. Additionally, 3 students expressed less confidence, citing their unfamiliarity with the projects being worked on as a reason. Only 1 student in Group A expressed uncertainty about evaluating a peer's project.

In Group B, 8 students expressed confidence, while 4 expressed less confidence. One student in Group B felt less confident in evaluating work due to their limited knowledge. The results were nearly the same between Group A and Group B, with reasons for less confidence in evaluating peer projects mainly being attributed to the early stage of learning and insufficient knowledge.

Regarding students' confidence in creating projects, in Group A, 6 students expressed confidence, 2 were less confident, and 4 were uncertain. Students who were confident could envision various projects they could create with the practical materials available. Among the 6 confident students in Group A, 4 were able to envision what type of robot they would build, including moisture-detecting robots, automatic hand sanitizers, automated trash bins, plant watering robots, and motion-activated robots. The majority of students who were uncertain cited their limited knowledge about Arduino as a reason. In Group B, 4 students expressed confidence, 3 planned to create line-following robots, and one planned to create an automatic hand sanitizer. One student felt less confident, and 4 felt uncertain. The lack of confidence among students in creating projects was mainly due to their limited knowledge about Arduino.

In terms of students' confidence in completing difficult tasks, in Group A, 10 students expressed confidence, and 2 were less confident. One student expressed confidence due to the availability of practical materials and clear, easy-to-follow modules. Another student expressed confidence because they understood the concept well at the initial stage. In Group B, 7 students expressed confidence, 1 was less confident, and 4 were uncertain. One student who expressed confidence mentioned the availability of platforms or tutorials to help in case of difficulties. Comparatively, students in Group A had more confidence in completing difficult tasks.

Confidence in Overcoming Obstacles

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 2 interview questions assessing students' confidence in producing accurate and appropriate projects and their willingness to attempt difficult projects.

In Group A, 50% or 6 out of 12 students expressed strong confidence in producing accurate projects, with one student even stating their ability to analyze potential errors. Additionally, 5 students expressed confidence, while 1 student expressed less confidence. In Group B, 3 students expressed strong confidence, 6 expressed confidence, and 3 expressed less confidence. A comparison of the interview results between the two groups showed that in the group with illustrated modules, or Group A, more students felt very confident in producing accurate and appropriate projects, and some could even analyze potential errors.

Based on the interview results in the above level category, the following conclusions or averages can be drawn as depicted in the figure below:

Fig. 2. Level Category Self-Efficacy

Strength

Strength aspect consists of 3 indicators, each of which is developed into 5 interview questions. The results of the interview analysis for each indicator are as follows:

Utilizing Experience

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 1 interview question. From the interview results in Group A, it was found that 6 students preferred to first try on their own based on their experience, while the other 6 students chose to ask friends or professors. Students who chose to try on their own first believed that they could consult other resources before seeking help from professors or other students. In Group B, 7 students stated they would try on their own first, while 5 students preferred to directly ask professors or other classmates for assistance.

Ability to Handle Diverse Situations

To assess this capability, the researcher used 2 interview questions: one to evaluate students' efforts to improve their grades and the other to gauge their willingness to persevere with robotics. Based on the interview analysis, for the first question in Group A, it was found that 100% of the students in this group would make a sincere effort to improve their grades. In Group B, 11 students expressed their intention to improve their grades, while 1 student responded with less optimism about their grades. From the comparison of these two interview results, more students in Group A showed enthusiasm to improve their grades compared to Group B.

Regarding the second question about students' willingness to diligently learn robotics, in Group A, all students expressed their commitment to learning robotics, especially Arduino, more diligently. One of the reasons motivating students to study robotics diligently included the availability of easy-to-follow modules, while others mentioned that IoT with Arduino robotics made learning more engaging. In Group B, 9 students stated they would study more diligently, while 3 students responded with less optimism. One student who expressed a commitment to study more diligently stated that seeing the original form of a robot made them interested.

From the figure above, it can be observed that there is a difference in the interview results in the level category between Group A and Group B. The percentage of Group A students who lacked confidence in the level category was 8%, or 1 student, while in Group B, the percentage of students lacking confidence in the level category was 25%, or 3 students. Based on these results, it is evident that students using modules with comprehensive illustrations have a more positive outlook on the level category.

Confidence in the Overall Learning Process

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 2 interview questions: one to assess students' understanding of the material taught and another to determine if students feel challenged by the material. The interview results from Group A showed that 11 students understood the material well, while only 1 student felt they had a lesser understanding of the material taught. The student who felt they understood less believed they were overly reliant on the module. They felt that without referring to the module, they couldn't grasp the material. This student tended to provide more pessimistic responses to the previous interview questions. In Group B, the interview results were the same as in Group A. 11 students stated they understood the material well, while 1 other student felt they had a lesser understanding of the material taught.

From the interview results for the second question, it was found that both Group A and Group B had the same outcome. In both groups, 11 students felt challenged to follow the lessons, while 1 student felt less challenged by the material taught. Students in Group A stated they felt challenged because there were always new projects to work on and they were motivated to work on projects to help other students. Students in Group B tended to have difficulty articulating why they felt challenged by the material taught. From the comparison of these two classes, it can be seen that students in Group A, or those learning with illustrated modules, were better able to express their interest in the material taught.

Based on the interview results for the strength category with the 3 indicators above, the following conclusions were drawn:

Fig. 3. Strength Category Self-Efficacy

From the above figure, it is known that there is the same result between Group A and Group B. From this similarity, it is evident that there is no difference between the group using illustrated modules and the group that does not use illustrations for the strength category.

Generality

In the strength aspect, there are 3 indicators, each of which is developed into 6 interview questions. The results of the interview analysis for each indicator are as follows:

Confidence in Self-Potential

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 3 interview questions: to assess students' confidence in completing projects on time, confidence in completing projects to the best of their ability, and confidence in completing projects independently.

The results of the first interview question in Group A showed that 9 students stated they were very confident in completing projects on time, while 3 students expressed less confidence. The 3 students who felt less confident cited several external factors, such as being unfamiliar with the LMS used and the overlapping deadlines with other assignments. In Group B, 3 students stated they were very confident in completing projects on time, 7 students expressed confidence, and 2 students felt less confident. From these results, it is known that students in Group A, or those with illustrated module materials, are more likely to feel very confident in completing projects on time.

For the second question, regarding efforts to complete projects to the best of their ability, the results showed that 7 students in Group A felt very confident, 4 students were confident, and only 1 student expressed less confidence. In Group B, 4 students stated they were very confident, 7 students were confident, and 1 student felt less confident. From the comparison of the two groups, it was found that more students in Group A felt confident in making efforts to complete projects to the best of their ability. One student in Group A mentioned that the provided module materials made them very confident in completing projects to the best of their ability.

The results of the third interview question, regarding confidence in completing projects independently, showed that in Group A, 6 students felt very confident in completing projects independently, 2 students were confident, and 4 other students felt less confident in their abilities. Some students who expressed less confidence in completing projects independently cited the novelty of robotics and the varying possibilities of errors as reasons, requiring assistance from other students to complete projects. In Group B, 5 students stated they were very confident, 4 students were confident, 2 students felt less confident, and 1 student expressed uncertainty. From these results, it is known that in Group B, or the group with non-illustrated module materials, there is actually a stronger belief in the ability to complete projects independently.

Belief in not giving up easily

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 1 question, namely whether students would try to use other learning resources to complete the project. The interview results showed that all students from both groups stated that they would try to find other sources to complete the project. This indicates that all students are not easily giving up in completing the given project.

Belief in completing tasks well

To measure this indicator, the researcher used 2 questions, namely whether students will complete their project independently and whether students will be more diligent in future learning. The interview results showed that in group A, 8 students were very confident in completing their tasks independently, while 4 other students stated that they would ask for help from friends. In group B, 7 students stated that they would complete their tasks independently, 3 students would ask for help, and 2 students were not sure. For the second question, the results were almost the same in both groups, with the majority of students stating that they would study harder in the next lessons, although some were not too sure.

Fig. 4. Level Category Self-Efficacy

From the above interview results, it is apparent that the results in the generality category are the same as those in the strength category. Both groups have the same percentage of test results, and there is no difference between group A and group B. This indicates that there is no difference in students' beliefs between those using illustrated modules and those not using illustrations.

Conclusion

The researcher will present the observation results regarding the impact of using Arduino robots or robotics on students' self-efficacy. In this study, the researcher used two groups: Group A with illustrated modules and Group B with non-illustrated modules. From the three categories of self-efficacy studied, it was found that with the assistance of Arduino robots, students have confidence in their ability to engage in learning. From the average interview results, it was found that 92% of students from both groups stated that they were very confident or confident in engaging in learning. Only 8%, or 2 students, expressed less confidence. These results indicate a positive influence of robotics on students' self-efficacy. This aligns with the findings of Aristawati et al. (Aristawati, Budiyanto, & Yuana, 2018), who reported that the use of robotics has a positive impact on students' self-efficacy. Additionally, the study by Leonard et al. (Leonard et al., 2017) suggests that the use of robotics can even enhance students' self-efficacy.

Based on the research findings, the researcher also identified differences between Group A and Group B. In Group A, 42% of students were very confident in their self-efficacy, while in Group B, only 17% expressed such confidence. These results indicate that the use of illustrations in robotics learning modules leads to greater confidence in students' abilities.

Based on the level of achievement in projects completed, Group A showed slightly better results, particularly in the abstraction criterion. This outcome is associated with the use of different modules between Group A and Group B. Group A utilized illustrated modules, while Group B did not. Yunita (Utami, 2020) found in her research that learning with illustrations can enhance students' understanding. Similarly, Sevarkodiyon et al. (As & Parimalafathima, 2014) concluded that illustrative methods are more effective than conventional ones.

These findings align with the research on Group A, which had higher abstraction scores compared to Group B. Although the use of illustrations did not impact other criteria, it influenced abstraction. This is positive, considering the lack of research on the relationship between illustrations and achievement.

Illustrations also affected students' self-efficacy. Interview assessments revealed that Group A demonstrated better self-efficacy compared to Group B, particularly in the level category. This suggests that students using illustrated modules are more enthusiastic about learning. They are also more confident in analyzing and describing their projects and those of their peers.

However, the use of different modules did not affect the strength and generality categories. Both groups had similar scores in these areas. Overall, illustrated modules contributed to better self-efficacy, especially in the level category, making students more enthusiastic and skilled at analyzing projects.

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